

Simplicity of A_n

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In *Simplicity of A_n* , <https://kconrad.math.uconn.edu/blurbs/grouptheory/Ansimple.pdf>, Keith Conrad gives five proofs of the simplicity of A_n for $n \geq 5$. We use below some of the ideas contained in Conrad's text. (A short proof of the fact that the sign of a permutation is well defined is given at the end of the text *The dimension of a finitely generated vector space* <https://zenodo.org/records/13740597>.)

Let n be an integer ≥ 5 .

Theorem 1. *The alternating group A_n is simple.*

Write e for the identity permutation of S_n , and call the product of two disjoint transpositions a *bi-transposition*.

Lemma 2. *The 3-cycles generate A_n . The bi-transpositions also generate A_n . The 3-cycles are conjugate in S_n . The bi-transpositions also are conjugate in S_n .*

Lemma 3. *The only normal subgroup G of S_n contained in A_n such that $\{e\} \neq G$ is A_n .*

Proof of Lemma 2. The last two statements follow from the fact that permutations with the same cycle structure are conjugate in S_n . Clearly the 3-cycles and the bi-transpositions, taken together, generate A_n . Hence it suffices to show that a 3-cycles is a product of bi-transpositions, and that a bi-transposition is a product of 3-cycles. But we have

$$(1\ 2\ 3) = (1\ 2)(4\ 5) \cdot (4\ 5)(2\ 3)$$

(here we use the assumption $n \geq 5$) and

$$(1\ 2)(3\ 4) = (1\ 2)(2\ 3)(2\ 3)(3\ 4) = (1\ 2\ 3)(2\ 3\ 4).$$

□

Proof of Lemma 3. For s in S_n we define $f(s)$ as the number of those i in $\{1, \dots, n\}$ which satisfy $s(i) \neq i$. Let $g_0 \in G$ be such that $f(g_0)$ is minimum among the $f(g)$ with $g \in G \setminus \{e\}$. Claim: $f(g_0) \in \{3, 4\}$. Clearly $f(g_0) \geq 3$. To show $f(g_0) \leq 4$, note that, if g is in $G \setminus \{e\}$, if t is a transposition in S_n , and if we set $c := tgtg^{-1}$, then we get $c = (tgt)g^{-1} \in G$, and $f(c) \leq 4$ because $c = t(gtg^{-1})$ is a product of two transpositions. This proves the claim. Now, if $f(g_0) = 3$, then g_0 is a 3-cycles, and if $f(g_0) = 4$, then g_0 is a bi-transposition. In both cases the result follows from Lemma 2. □

Proof of Theorem 1. Assume by contradiction that there is a normal subgroup G of A_n such that $\{e\} \neq G \neq A_n$. Let $t \in S_n$ be a transposition, and set $G' := tGt$. It is easily seen that G' does not depend on t and is again a normal subgroup G of A_n such that $\{e\} \neq G' \neq A_n$. Then Lemma 3 implies $G' \neq G$. The sets $G \cap G'$ and $GG' = G'G$ are normal subgroups of A_n . We claim that they are normal even in S_n . Indeed, if $t \in S_n$ is a transposition, we have

$$t(G \cap G')t = tGt \cap tG't = G' \cap G = G \cap G',$$

$$t(GG')t = (tGt)(tG't) = G'G = GG'.$$

This proves the claim, and, in view of Lemma 3, this implies $G \cap G' = \{e\}$ and $GG' = A_n$. Moreover the order $|G|$ of G satisfies $|G|^2 = n!/2$, so $|G|$ is even, and G has an order two element g . We can assume

$$g = (1\ 2)(3\ 4) \cdots (2k-1\ 2k)$$

with $2 \leq 2k \leq n$. Setting $t := (1\ 2)$ we get $tgt = g$, that is $g \in G \cap G'$, contradiction. □

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